

Analyze Industry and Construction Group Structure in Vietnam Economy for Sustainable Development

Author's Details: Nguyen Quang Thai¹ Bui Trinh²

Prof, Dr. Vietnam development research

Institute Dr, **Correspondence author.** Vietnam development research

Institute - Email address: buitrinhcan@gmail.com

Abstract

For many years, Vietnam has had a relatively high growth rate of gross domestic product (GDP) compared to other countries in the region, an average increase of 6.2% in the period 2005 - 2018. However, the macroeconomic instability such as the budget deficit, public debt, and debt of the economy, are always high, the environment has many potential risks.

This study used an input – output system in order to show the status of the Vietnam economic structure. Especially the industry and construction group in the sustainable development of Vietnam. The study shows that the final demand of this sectors group does not spread much to the value added, but strongly spreads to imports and greenhouse gas emissions. There seems to be a deviation in the economic structure in Vietnam due to the inadequate "policy" resources for sustainable development.

Key Words: Input, output, structure, sustainable, Vietnam

I. INTRODUCTION.

Sustainable development is a new concept that defines development in all aspects of current society while ensuring continued development in the far future. June 29, 2019, Vietnam's Prime Minister addresses the G20 Summit at a climate-environment session emphasizing climate change, environmental pollution, and energy security instability. That is the survival of mankind! The Prime Minister's statement is a message of sustainable development. Development that if people die, then what does development do? Developed for whom? Recently, on August 12, 2019, at the plenary session of the sustainable development conference in 2019 in Hanoi, the Prime Minister noted, "... not because of rapid development, but forget about sustainable development factor".

For many years, Vietnam has had a relatively high growth rate of gross domestic product (GDP) compared to other countries in the region, an average increase of 6.2% in the period 2005 - 2018. However, the macroeconomic instability such as the budget deficit, public debt, and debt of the economy, are always high, the environment has many potential risks.

In Vietnam in the reports, even the research articles implicitly recognize the structure of sector II (industry and construction) and sector III (service sector) in GDP. It must be increased and regarded as an economic development in the right direction since then, the idea in economic restructuring is to promote both Region II and Region III. Capital stock of manufacturing is estimated from 53% of the total capital of the economy, but ironically, the ratio of value added per output of this sector according to the structure based on input-output table, was 34.1% until recent years (the structure of I / O Table 2016), this rate was only 21% (Bui Trinh, 2016). This means that the area is increasingly inefficient, leading to an increase in investment to offset that inefficiency. The ratio of intermediate costs to the production value of the manufacturing group is increasing day by day because the sector is increasingly outsourcing, many FDI projects have high production and export value but part of value received by Vietnam is only outsourcing and assembled.

The economic structure was proposed by W. Leontief (1941) to analyze the structural changes of the US economy based on the 1919 and 1929 interdisciplinary balance sheets. The input-output analysis has been developed by many modelers such as W. Leontief (1970), Schoonbeek, L. (1990), Ebiefung, AA, Udo, G. (1999), Dobos, I. and Floriska, A. (2005), Yu Fan et al. (2016). In this study, some key structures of Vietnam's economy are shown through the "direct cost," absorption matrix, which was developed by Chenery and Watanabe (1958), the inter-sectoral structure is determined through the Leontief standard relationship with the

intermediate cost matrix to reflect the linkage between industries and the relationship between final demand with output and added value.

Today, in parallel with the National System of Accounts (SNA), the United Nations also offers the System of Environmental-Economic Accounts (SEEA), if the inter-sectoral balance standard model is the center of SNA system, the Hybrid input-output framework is the center of the SEEA system.

In Vietnam, there are also some studies applying the input-output system in the analysis and measurement of economic structure in combination with capital matrix, a waste matrix such as K. Kobayashi, T. Bui (2011), T.Bui and Phong.NV (2013), Tu.TTT and authors (2016), Nguyen P. Thao (2016), T.Bui and Hoa.PL (2017)

II. Data source and treatment.

This research used the input-output tables, 2012 and 2016. The input-output table, 2012 of Vietnam, was published by the Vietnam general statistics office. The input-output table, 2016, was updated based on the input-output table, 2012 and data from enterprise survey that Vietnam general statistics office conducts every year. The steps for updating as follows:

1. Collection output and intermediate input vectors in 2016 (X^{2016} and II^{2016}) based on enterprise survey conducted by Vietnam general statistics office
2. The intermediate input matrix was estimated as follow:

$$X_{ij}^{2016} = (X_{ij}^{2012} / II_j^{2012}) * II_j^{2016}$$
 So $A^{2016} = (a_{2016ij} = X_{ij}^{2016} / X_j^{2016}) \neq A^{2012}$ (A is direct input coefficient) matrix
 Where: X_{ij} is sector j used product i for intermediate input
3. Final demand in 2016 was estimated based on data available from Vietnam general statistics office
4. Ras method was used for balancing gross output and gross input
5. Direct impact vector on greenhouse gas collected by “THE INITIAL BIENNIAL UPDATED REPORT OF VIET NAM TO THE UNITED NATIONS FRAMEWORK CONVENTION ON CLIMATE CHANGE” of Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment
6. The input-output tables were aggregated to 21 sectors as table 1

Table 1. Sectors

NO.	NAME OF SECTORS
1	Agriculture, forestry and fisheries
2	Extractive
3	Production of food, beverages and tobacco
4	Production of textile products, apparel and leather
5	Producing petroleum and gas products
6	Manufacture of chemical products
7	Producing non-metallic mineral products
8	Producing and processing metal and metal products
9	Manufacture of equipment and machinery
10	Other manufacturing and processing industries
11	Producing and distributing electricity, gas, hot water, steam and air conditioning
12	Water supply; activities of management and treatment of garbage and wastewater

13	Build
14	Transporting warehousing
15	Wholesale and retail; Hotel and restaurant
16	Information and communication
17	Financial activities, banking and insurance
18	Professional activities, science and technology
19	Education and training
20	Health and social assistance activities
21	Other service sectors

III. METHOD IN RESEARCH

Opinions on key sector development based on unbalanced growth theory or "growth poles" introduced in 1950. Typical representatives of this theory (A. Hirschman, F. Perrons) argue that supporting all sectors also means no support for any industry. The development of that industry on the principle of "choice and focus" and at the same time, achieving the highest efficiency, cannot and does not necessarily ensure sustainable growth by maintaining the inter-sectoral balance structure for all countries.

The identification of key sectors in an economy is also mentioned through researches by Chenery and Watanabe. These industries are defined as having a backward relationship (which is the link between the producer and the supplier of input materials for that manufacturer) and the forward link (which is the link between the manufacturing industry that product with its industry of use as its input) strong. At the same time, economists Ramussen and Hirschman have researched around relationships between sectors of the economy to give their views on key economic sectors, whereby these industries create several rounds of indirect demand in other sectors, as many within the industry to create more impact that motivation. The next relationship calculates the output of an industry affected how the expansion of a sector in the economy. The reaction of this industry which increasingly higher industry important to the economy.

From the basis of this theory in this study, the authors used the perspective of economists and Ramusse A. Hirschman: *"The economic sector is of key economic sectors likely to be motivated to growth development of other industries and the sustainable development of the country in the period of time specified."*

In fact, the key economic sector can be expressed in equivalent terms: key industry, spearhead economic sector, priority economic sector and competitive economic sector. In this study, the key economic sectors and key industries are equivalent.

According to economist Hirschman, two basic criteria for choosing the key industry are spillover (backward linkage) and sensitivity (forward linkage). Besides, due to the actual situation in each country, it is possible to include other indicators as a basis for selection. In some developing countries (including Vietnam), the trade deficit situation that occurred over the years caused the consequences of macroeconomic instability, which required more criteria to choose the key industry, points are less likely to cause the industry to stimulate imports. Along with that, now due to the pollution of the environment and climate change around the world is increasingly severe, hence, sustainable development, environmental protection is taken into consideration in the direction of global development, criteria spread to the environment are encouraged to make selection criteria for key sectors. Therefore, depending on the situation of the countries in each stage can choose different criteria for the selection of key sectors from which the most appropriate given the industry as key sectors in each period.

W. Leontief's I / O model stems from ideas in the "Capital" set of K. Marx when he found a direct relationship according to technical rules between the factors involved in the production process. This idea of K Marx was

later developed by Wassily Leontief (Nobel Economics, 1973) by the comprehensive mathematicalization of the supply-demand relation in the whole economy. W. Leontief considers each manufacturing technology (for a sufficiently short period of time, for example, a year) to be a linear relationship between the number of products produced on one side and the products on the other, substances and services as input costs. This relationship is represented by a linear function system with coefficients determined by the technological process. With this in mind, the first I/O table developed by W. Leontief for the United States was the I/O table in 1919 and 1929. Model balances interdisciplinary I/O allows quantitative indicators pervasive economic, sensitivity, spread to import and spread to the environment from which can make the basis of determining the economic sectors key of the economy.

Besides, there are currently two types of the inter-industry balance sheet, but in principle, the competitive import I/O is not as good as the non-competitive import I/O, because in the form of import. However, the I/O table does not distinguish between intermediate costs which are domestic products or imported from foreign countries. Therefore, when analyzing economic structure through diffuse indices or the sensitivity of the economy, policymakers will not be able to distinguish which sectors are really "key" sectors of the economy. Intersectoral balance sheet non-competitive format separated elements within and outside the country so it's a lot better reflect the sensitivity and spread of sectors in the economy. Besides, from the non-competitive inter-industry balance sheet, it is allowed to determine the coefficient of spillover to important industries.

This study applies Leontief's relationships based on Vietnam's 2012 and 2016 interdisciplinary balance sheets. As usual internal structure and interdisciplinary structure of the spread Forests of each bridge to provide interdisciplinary balance sheet represents a period of 5 years. The interdisciplinary balance sheet of 2012 can be representative of the economic structure for the period of 2010 - 2014 and the updated inter-sectoral balance sheet for 2016 represents the economic structure for the period of 2015-2020. The specific calculation method is presented in Appendix 1.

III. Research results

The results of the research on the diffusion index and the sensitivity from Table 2 show that the agriculture, forestry and fishery (sector 1), the food, beverage and tobacco processing industry (sector 3), producing petroleum and gas products (sector 5) and other manufacturing and processing industries (sector 10) that have both a high degree of spillover and a higher sensitivity than the general average of the economy and no change in the period 2010 - 2020, this shows that these 4 groups not only strongly stimulate other sectors in the economy but also the demand for input so the economy is also greater than the average of the economy. Most of the services sector is no index spread and sensitivity well, especially sectors of professional activities of science and technology with the spread and the sensitivity is lower than the average rate pretty much, this shows this industry group is not going to spread the sectors in the economy did not need it. Thus, the food and beverage industry group have the best spread to the production value of the economy, this means the end product of this sector will stimulate economic production in the processing industry.

Table 2. The index spread and the sensitivity of the economy

NO	ECONOMICS	2012				2016			
		Backlinks (BL)	The index spread	Forward link (FL)	Sensitivity	Backlinks (BL)	The index spread	Forward link (FL)	Sensitivity
1	Agriculture, forestry and seafood	1.688	1.104	2.299	1.504	2.181	1.109	3.180	1.616
2	Extractive	1.396	0.913	2.219	1.452	1.761	0.895	2.700	1.373
3	Manufacture of food, beverage and tobacco	2.263	1.480	1.657	1.084	2.769	1.408	2.000	1.017
4	Manufacture of textile products, apparel and leather goods	1.551	1.014	1.364	0.892	1.968	1.000	1.658	0.843
5	Manufacture of petroleum products and gas	1.749	1.144	1.923	1.258	2.207	1.122	2.994	1.522
6	Manufacture of chemical products	1.558	1.019	1.461	0.955	2.128	1.082	2.164	1.100
7	Manufacture of non-metallic mineral products	1.582	1.035	1.304	0.853	2.153	1.094	1.693	0.861
8	Producing and processing metal and metal products	1.464	0.957	1.752	1.146	1.935	0.983	2.764	1.405
9	Manufacture of equipment and machinery	1.377	0.901	1.294	0.846	1.747	0.888	1.977	1.005
10	Other manufacturing and processing industries	1.778	1.163	2.489	1.628	2.252	1.145	3.521	1.790
11	Producing and distributing electricity, gas, hot water, steam and air conditioning	1.183	0.774	1.337	0.874	1.505	0.765	1.563	0.795
12	Water supply; activities of management and treatment of garbage and waste water	1.385	0.906	1.106	0.724	1.819	0.925	1.167	0.593
13	Construction	1.697	1.110	1.153	0.754	2.110	1.073	1.229	0.625
14	Warehouse transportation	1.603	1.048	1.442	0.943	2.068	1.051	1.731	0.880
15	Wholesale and retail; Hotel and restaurant	1.466	0.959	1.722	1.126	1.905	0.968	2.230	1.134
16	Information and communication	1.538	1.006	1.420	0.929	1.908	0.970	1.654	0.841
17	Financial activities, banking and insurance	1.363	0.892	1.546	1.011	1.775	0.903	1.917	0.974
18	Professional activities, science and technology	1.355	0.886	1.229	0.804	1.819	0.925	1.515	0.770
19	Education and training	1.184	0.775	1.029	0.673	1.542	0.784	1.045	0.531
20	Health and social assistance activities	1.655	1.082	1.008	0.659	2.080	1.057	1.011	0.514
21	Other service sectors	1.271	0.831	1.353	0.885	1.679	0.854	1.597	0.812

Source: Calculated from I / O 2012 table of TCTK and updated by the research team

Combining sensitivity and diffusion provides a picture of industry linkage. Figures 1 and 2 show that in the past 10 years, the picture of industry linkages has hardly changed significantly. Although the sectoral link has not changed, the efficiency level through the ratio of added value to the production value of the period 2015-2020 is inferior to the period of 2010-2014 in most sectors, segment 2010 - 2014 rate increased value compared to the value of about 36%, the production period from 2015 to 2020 shows that this percentage drops to 28%. This rate dropped the most especially in the manufacturing and processing industry. This partly reflects the level of outsourcing of Vietnam's economy increasingly high!

Figure 3. Picture of industry linkages (Economic - Landscape), phase 2015-2020

Source: Research team's calculations

Figure 4. Picture of industry linkages, phase 2010-2014

Source: Research team's calculations

Figure 5. The ratio of added value to the production value

Source: The research team calculated from the I/O panel in 2012 and 2016

Spread from the last demand to imports and the added value

Research on sensitivity and pervasive as in newspeak to the spread of demand to production value, in many cases, increase the demand stimulates supply side but also stimulate imports without spreading to added value, further research shows how spillover of some industries (4 sectors) spreads to production but also to value-added ($GDP = \sum \text{value added at base price} + \text{product tax}$), how to import? An industry that is considered to be of importance to the economy is one that has a spillover index, high sensitivity but must spread to low imports and spread to high added value. Table 3 shows that of the 4 sectors with high indices and high sensitivity, only agriculture, forestry and seafood groups meet this requirement. *Most of the manufacturing and processing industries, although having high indices and high sensitivities, have strongly stimulated imports and spreaded to added values much lower than the average.* This shows that the manufacturing and processing industry in Vietnam is mainly processing and increasingly higher levels of processing. Another interesting thing is that most of the service sector index, low import diffuse and spread to the added value is higher than the average, but these industries have spread index and relatively low sensitivity. To improve this issue can offer important solutions if Vietnam *Increasing the auxiliary products for manufacturing and processing industry groups to meet the input for service groups and the dancing industry must also develop to meet the needs of other sectors in the economy.* Since that would make the sector linkages raised through the spread and increased sensitivity, thereby creating a strong momentum of economic development of the country.

However, "policy resources," especially tax policies, have not been directed to this issue. For example, there are two problems with indirect taxes, firstly, indirect taxes for FDI enterprises are preferential in tax policies; most of FDI enterprises are processing then exporting. These enterprises are directly exporting, so import inputs are given tax incentives, while domestic businesses are not entitled to tax incentives if they sell domestically.

It can be seen that the call for the production of ancillary products for the past ten years is just a formality and slogan. The import-export tax policy does not show any action proving the flatness among types of enterprises and secondly, when most of the production is processed in Vietnam then Vietnamese people actually use Vietnamese goods as well as using imported goods in other forms, using products of FDI in this case, too, so when it comes to the contribution of FDI to the budget necessary to separate indirect taxes and corporate income tax. Since indirect taxes are contributed by the Vietnamese people, FDI businesses only contribute to corporate income tax.

Table 3. Spillover from an increasing unit of final demand to value added and imports

NO	ECONOMICS	2012			2016		
		Spread to VA of the rising unit of the last demand	Spread to VA b/q	The degree of spread to imports	Spread to VA of the rising unit of the last demand	Spread to VA b/q	The degree of spread to imports
1	Agriculture, forestry and seafood	0.684	1.024	0.952	0.640	1.050	0.922
2	Extractive	0.654	0.979	1.042	0.585	0.960	1.062
3	Manufacture of food, beverage and tobacco	0.625	0.935	1.130	0.580	0.953	1.074
4	Manufacture of textile products, apparel and leather goods	0.560	0.838	1.327	0.511	0.839	1.251
5	Manufacture of petroleum products and gas	0.483	0.722	1.560	0.431	0.707	1.456
6	Manufacture of chemical products	0.511	0.765	1.474	0.493	0.809	1.297
7	Manufacture of non-metallic mineral products	0.663	0.992	1.016	0.619	1.016	0.975
8	Producing and processing metal and metal products	0.431	0.645	1.716	0.413	0.678	1.502
9	Manufacture of equipment and machinery	0.388	0.581	1.845	0.375	0.615	1.600
10	Other manufacturing and processing industries	0.538	0.806	1.392	0.514	0.844	1.243
11	Producing and distributing electricity, gas, hot water, steam and air conditioning	0.879	1.316	0.364	0.763	1.253	0.606
12	Water supply; activities of management and treatment of garbage and wastewater	0.772	1.154	0.689	0.690	1.133	0.793
13	Construction	0.578	0.864	1.274	0.538	0.883	1.183
14	Warehouse transportation	0.604	0.904	1.193	0.555	0.911	1.138
15	Wholesale and retail; Hotel and restaurant	0.798	1.195	0.608	0.724	1.189	0.706
16	Information and communication	0.682	1.020	0.959	0.608	0.998	1.003
17	Financial activities, banking and insurance	0.869	1.300	0.396	0.798	1.309	0.517
18	Professional activities, science and technology	0.822	1.230	0.536	0.714	1.171	0.733
19	Education and training	0.928	1.388	0.218	0.830	1.363	0.434
20	Health and social assistance activities	0.680	1.018	0.964	0.614	1.008	0.988
21	Other service sectors	0.886	1.325	0.345	0.799	1.311	0.515

Source: Calculated by the research team from I/O tables 2012 and 2016
 Affect the environment

This study due to limited data sources should only study of economic impacts of GHG emissions (Greenhouse Gas - GHG). Greenhouse gas emissions include CO₂, CH₄ và N₂O, calculated based on the Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment’s report on climate change¹. The results show that the economic indicators of agriculture, forestry and seafood have impressive indicators, the situation from the current economic structure shows that this group emits to the environment the amount of greenhouse gas emissions which is more than 2 times higher than the general emission level of the economy in the whole 10-year period(each inter-sector balance sheet represents 5 years).Remarkably, the amount of greenhouse gas emissions is on the rise (Figure

¹ Vietnam Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment“THE INITIAL BIENNIAL UPDATED REPORT OF VIET NAM TO THE UNITED NATIONS FRAMEWORK CONVENTION ON CLIMATE CHANGE” VIET NAM PUBLISHING HOUSE OF NATURAL RESOURCES, ENVIRONMENT AND CARTOGRAPHY, 2014

4).The sector that emits the highest greenhouse effect is the group of non-metallic mineral products (sector 7), 3.3 times higher than the average.Then the construction industry (2.39 times), the agriculture, forestry and seafood (2.36 times);water supply; waste management and treatment activities, wastewater; other manufacturing and processing industries; production of food, beverages and tobacco; extractive,all have higher greenhouse gas emissions than the general level of the economy.One thing to note is that most people think the transportation industry emits a large greenhouse effect but it is not, the transportation industry emits relatively large amounts of CO₂ but doesn't emit much CH₄ and N₂O. ***Most of the service sector not only spread to higher earnings but also spread to the lower atmosphere.***

For sustainable development, it is necessary to direct resources into sustainable development for agriculture, so that agriculture becomes "green agriculture."

Concentrate resources to improve the technological process for the processing industry of agricultural products so that this sector spreads to more income and reduces waste to the environment.

As the service sectors are well-spread to value added, less spillover to imports and greenhouse gas emissions, in order to increase the spillover indices and sensitivity for this sector, policy direction for the processing industry is needed to create products of ancillary products as input for the service sector, and service-oriented groups are essential needs for other sectors of the economy.Policymakers need to change their perceptions about industry structure in value added; the service sector should be focused instead of the manufacturing industry.

Research shows that the most important resource is the "resource policy"

Change the method of attracting FDI, gradually escape from processing traps, concentrate land resources for the selected industries (fields) for sustainable development.

Table 4 shows that the structure of demand to supply tends to change in a deteriorating direction, the structure of the period 2015 - 2020 shows the spread of demand factors to higher production values than in 2010 - 2014 but spread to lower added value and spread to stronger imports. This proves that the assumption that Vietnam's economy is increasingly processed and the slogan "Vietnamese people use Vietnamese goods" does not seem appropriate anymore.It is noteworthy that exports of goods spill over to the lowest added value, but are strongly spill over to imports, making it more dangerous to produce for export of goods that cause the largest greenhouse gas emissions in elements of final demand, while service exports cause the least greenhouse effect but best spread to income.

In a report of the Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment, the GHG emissions are estimated at 247 million tons by 2010, the team's calculations show that the amount of GHG to 2012 is 300 million tons and by 2016 is 423 million tons.Report of the Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment Forecasts to 2020 greenhouse gas emissions at 466 million tonnes, according to calculations by the study structure construction industry at present, the amount of greenhouse gas emissions to 2020 bow approximately 600 million tons.Tăng trưởng về khí nhà kính bình quân từ năm 2010 – 20120 khoảng 7,5%. The average growth of greenhouse gases from 2010 - 20120 is about 7.5%, faster than the average GDP growth rate during this period (about 6.3%).This is in contrast to the policy of prioritizing the export of goods in both tax and credit policies. It seems that capital and policy resources are again misplaced.

Table 4. Spreading from the factors of domestic demand last economic factors and environmental

	2012					2016				
	Final consumption	Investment / Accumulation	Exports of goods	Export of services	Total (Million tons)	Final consumption	Investment / Accumulation	Exports of goods	Export of services	Total (Million tons)
Spread to production	1.744	1.799	1.788	1.601		2.053	2.128	2.094	1.911	
Spread to added value	0.72	0.58	0.56	0.76		0.66	0.54	0.52	0.69	
Spread to imports	0.28	0.42	0.44	0.24		0.34	0.46	0.48	0.31	
Estimated GHG emissions (million tonnes tonnes)	77	65	152	6	300	140	100	176	7	423
Structure of GHG	25.7%	21.7%	50.7%	1.9%	100%	33,28%	23,51%	41,6%	1,7%	100%

Source: Calculations of the research team based on I/O and data from the Ministry of Natural Resources – Environment.

Figure 4. Greenhouse gas emissions in the period 2010 - 2014 and the period of 2015 - 2020 caused in the production process.

Source: Calculations based on the team’s Resources Ministry – Environment report and the I/O panel, 2012 and 2016.

IV. Conclusions and policy implications

+ If the structure of the industry group accounted for in current GDP or more and tended to more unfavorable for the economy even causes enormous damage to the environment, as the manufacturing industry spreads low to added value but spreads sharply to greenhouse gas emissions.

+ The agriculture, forestry and seafood sectors spread well to income but also spread to the environment, so it is necessary to industrialize this industry in the direction of green agriculture.

+ While the production structure of industrial groups has not been changed yet, it is necessary to introduce strict regulations on waste management and treatment. Need to focus on industrial sectors processing agricultural products, forestry and fisheries. This group of industries has a low coefficient of spread to high added value and spread to imports. This processing industry group needs to change its technological processes to reduce waste to the environment. The structure of the industry within 2025 is proposed in Table 5. The structure of the mining industry and other processing industries decreases while the processing of agricultural products increases.

Table 5. Structure of some sectors in the industry

	CURRENT STRUCTURE	2025	2030
Extractive	17.2	16.9	16.4
Manufacture of food, beverage and tobacco	11.8	12.4	13.0
Manufacture of textile products, apparel and leather goods	18.0	18.0	18.0
Manufacture of petroleum products and gas	3.9	3.9	3.9
Manufacture of chemical products	5.2	5.2	5.2
Manufacture of non-metallic mineral products	5.2	5.2	5.2
Producing and processing metal and metal products	8.4	8.4	8.4
Manufacture of equipment and machinery	12.9	12.9	12.9
Other manufacturing and processing industries	17.3	17.1	17.0
Total	100	100	100.0

Source: Calculated by authors

+ Industry Vietnam is actually the industry processing and assembling dependent on FDI huge amount of added value is very low and the content of the added value that the Vietnam get much lower but polluting the environment most. Thus, for sustainable development by 2025, this group needs to reduce the structure in GDP by 2 percentage points (from 34% of GDP to 32% of GDP) and the service sector needs to increase to 44% of GDP. Structure of agriculture, forestry and seafood sectors remained unchanged then the economy can both grow well and reduce pollution. According to the calculation, by 2030, the structure of the three sectors should be services: 45%, construction industry: 30% and agriculture, forestry and fisheries: 14%, this structure is good for growth and minimizing house emissions. Note that the agroforestry structure increases not only for agriculture but also for forest planting, tending and protection to improve forest quality in order to reduce greenhouse gas emissions of the economy effectively.

+ If the policy focus on industry and exports (the proportion of exports of industrial products accounted for a large proportion) can increase an indicator identifiable accomplishments such as GDP but the people and the country for nothing but the resources of the economy increasingly weakened by the cash flows paid overseas property growing. The growth rate of cash flow of ownership is much higher than GDP growth (In 2017, according to the General Statistics Office, net foreign ownership payment was nearly 11 billion USD, accounting for 5% of GDP and the ratio of GNI to GDP was only about 95%) – See appendix 2.

+ FDI enterprises accounted for nearly 60% of the production value of the whole industry (including mining) and 73% in value of exports of goods, so the structure 3 group of sectors and structures within the industry

implies that the need to improve the quality of FDI towards economic sustainability and the environment. The structure in Table 5 and Figure 5 could cause GDP to increase by 2.1% to 2025 and 2.5% to 2030. Changing forest quality, improving technology to make agriculture "greener" can reduce GHG emissions by 4.5% by 2025 and 9% by 2030 (in the case of the CO₂ absorption coefficient of the forest (LULUCF)² increased to 0,02 and 0,04 percentage points and the agricultural emission factor decreased by 0,1 – 0,3%). By attracting and managing FDI effectively, the cash flow of ownership payments will decrease.

REFERENCES

- i. Albert O. Hirschman (1958) *The Strategy of Economic Development*, Yale University Press Volume 10
- ii. Asian Development Bank (2015). *Financial Soundness Indicators for Financial Sector Stability in Vietnam*. Manila.
- iii. CHENERY, H. B., WATANABE (1958), T. *International comparisons of the structure of production*. *Econometrica*, v. 26, n., p. 487-521, 958.
- iv. Guo, D. and Hewings, G. J. D. (2001). *Comparative Analysis of China's Economic Structures between 1987 and 1997: An Input-Output Prospective*. Discussion Paper at Regional Economics Applications Laboratory. Urbana.
- v. HADDAD, E. A. (1997) *Regional inequality and structural changes in the Brazilian economy*. Illinois: University of Illinois at Ur-ban-Champaign, Dissertation.
- vi. HADDAD, E. A., HEWINGS, G. J. D. (1998) *Trade Liberalization and regional competitiveness in the Brazilian economy*. In: *ADVANCED STUDIES INSTITUTE IN REGIONAL SCIENCE*, 11, 1998, München. Anais. München: Summer Institute.
- vii. Iris Claus. Kathy Li (2003) "New Zealand's Production Structure: An International Comparison" *NZ TREASURY WORKING PAPER 03/16*
- viii. Miller, R. E. and Blair, P. D. (1985). *Input-output analysis foundation and extension*. Prentice-Hall, Inc: New Jersey.
- ix. Ministry of National Resource and Environment "THE INITIAL BIENNIAL UPDATED REPORT OF VIET NAM TO THE UNITED NATIONS FRAMEWORK CONVENTION ON CLIMATE CHANGE" VIET NAM PUBLISHING HOUSE OF NATURAL RESOURCES, ENVIRONMENT AND CARTOGRAPHY, 2014
- x. Nguyễn Hồng Sơn Dịch vụ Việt nam 2020: Hướng tới chất lượng, hiệu quả và hiện đại. iNXB Đại học Quốc gia Hà Nội, 2010
- xi. Sonis, M. and Hewings, G. J. D. (1999). *Economic landscapes: Multiplier product matrix analysis for multiregional input-output systems*. *Hitotsubashi Journal of Economics*, 40(1): 59–74.
- xii. Trinh Bui (2015) *A study on the Input-Output System for evaluation of infrastructure development in Vietnam*. , Kyoto University.
- xiii. Trinh Bui, Dương Mạnh Hùng "Hiệu quả đầu tư thông qua hệ số ICOR" *Tạp chí kinh tế và dự báo*, số 447, 2009
- xiv. Trinh Bui, Kiyoshi Kobayashi, Nguyen Van Huan, Pham Le Hoa (2012) *An Integrated Framework for Multi-Purposes Socio-Economic Analysis Based on Input-Output Model*, *British Journal of Economics, Finance and Management Sciences*, Vol 4
- xv. Trinh Bui, Nguyen Viet Phong (2013) *A short note on Ras method* *Advances in Management & Applied Economics*, vol. 3, no.4, 133-137
- xvi. Trinh Bui, Phong. N. V, Quoc Bui *The RAS Method with Random Fixed points*, *Journal of Economics and Business*, Vol.1, No.4, 640- 646.
- xvii. Trinh Bui and Pham, L. H. (2014). *Comparing the Economic Structure and Carbon Dioxide Emission between China and Vietnam*, *International Journal of Economics and Financial Research*, Vol. 3, No. 3, pp: 31-38, 2017

²Land Use, Land-Use Change and Forestry

- xviii. To TrungThanh, Nguyen, V. P. and Trinh Bu (2016). *Some comparisons between the Vietnam and china"s economic structure, policy implications. Advances in Management & Applied Economics, 6(3): 153-66.*
- xix. Wassily, L. (1941). *Structure of the American economy, 1919-1929. Harverd University Press: Cambridge Mass.*

Appendix 1. Input – output analysis and environment impacts

Standard non-competitive Leontief relationship:

$$A.X + Y = X \tag{1}$$

X is a vector of production value, $A = (a_{ij})_{(n \times n)}$ the coefficient matrix direct costs with $a_{ij} = X_{ij}/X_j$, Y is the last demand vector and n is the number of trades.

$$Y = C + G + I + E - M \tag{2}$$

Analyzing the matrix A and the vector Y into the use of domestic and imported products, equation (1) can be rewritten:

$$A^d.X + A^m.X + C^d + C^m + G^d + G^m + I^d + I^m + E = X \tag{3}$$

$$\text{Call } C^d + G^d + I^d + E = Y^d$$

$$\text{And notice that } A^m.X + C^m + G^m + I^m = M$$

From equation (1), (2) and (3) we have:

$$A^d.X + Y^d = X \tag{4}$$

And the Leontief relation for the non-competitive interdisciplinary balance model:

$$X = (I - A^d)^{-1}.Y^d \tag{5}$$

With A^d being the coefficient matrix of intermediate cost directly using domestic products, $(I - A^d)^{-1}$ is the Leontief inverse matrix and Y^d is the domestic final demand matrix, which includes the final consumption of domestic products, accumulating domestically produced and exported products.

The index of backlinks (BL) and forward links (FL) is determined as follows:

Let matrix $B = (I - A^d)^{-1}$ be the Leontief matrix.

Backlinks are identified:

$B_j = \sum B_{ij}$; reflects the expansion of an industry when using products of another industry as input costs.

Forward link:

$B_i = \sum B_{ij}$ pointed out, the level of production depends on inputs from other industries.

Guo and Hewings (2001) explain that as the backward linkage increases, there will be greater demand for other industries' inputs and the upward linkage will lead to a change in the sensitivity of other sectors' output.

From these ideas the diffusion index and the sensitivity of each industry were determined:

$$\text{Spillover index: } P_j = B_j. (n / T) \tag{6}$$

$$\text{The sensitivity: } S_i = B_i. (n / T) \tag{7}$$

Here: n is the number of sectors surveyed in the I/O table; $T = \sum \sum B_{ij}$

The combination of the sensitivity and the spread of each industry shows the relative importance of that sector to the economy. This combination is defined as the “multiplier product matrix” of the Leontief system (Guo, Hewing, 2001) (T.Bui, Hoa P.L, 2017):

$$M = S.P \tag{8}$$

For: $S = (S_i)_{(n \times 1)}$ and $P = (P_j)_{(1 \times n)}$ and $M = (M_{ij})_{(n \times n)}$ are considered as “Economic context - Economic - Landscape” at a time and show the structure interdisciplinary at that time.

Calculating the impact of demand on output X and value added is used as follows:

Impact of final domestic demand on output X: $\sum(I-A^d)^{-1} \cdot Y^d \div \sum Y^d$

The impact of final domestic demand on added value v: $X \div \sum Y^d$

The impact of final domestic demand on environmental: e: $X \div \sum Y^d$

Here: v is a vector of value added coefficient, e is a vector of environmental coefficient, \div represents the scalar division

Appendix 2. GNI, GDP and net, property incomes at current prices

	Gross national income (VND billion) - GNI	Gross domestic product (VND billion) - GDP	Outward payment of net ownership (VND billion)	The ratio of gross national income to gross domestic product (%) GNI/GDP
2007	1,211,806	1,246,769	-34963	97.2
2008	1,567,964	1,616,047	-48083	97.02
2009	1,731,221	1,809,149	-77928	95.69
2010	2,075,578	2,157,828	-82250	96.19
2011	2,660,076	2,779,880	-119804	95.69
2012	3,115,227	3,245,419	-130192	95.99
2013	3,430,668	3,584,262	-153594	95.71
2014	3,750,823	3,937,856	-187033	95.25
2015	3,977,609	4,192,862	-215253	94.87
2016	4,314,321	4,502,733	-188412	95.82
Preliminary 2017	4,764,958	5,005,975	-241017	95.19
Average growth in 2007-2017 (%)	14.67	14.91	21.30	

Source: GSO – gso.gov.vn